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Teaching Professional skills in Engineering Programmes: The Academic Perspective

A plan for using Phenomenography to explore academic conceptions of their role in developing professional skills in engineering students

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ABSTRACT

Engineering graduates in today's world face a global industry where professional skills are as important as the intellectual prowess gained by obtaining a degree itself. The importance of these skills is abundant in literature, yet so too is an ongoing barrage from industry that Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) are not developing sufficient professional skills within students [1].

This occurs against a background of accrediting bodies who have adopted programme outcomes which require employability/professional skills to be integrated into the curriculum. There is also evidence that many educators have attempted to employ innovative strategies, such as Problem Based Learning to expose students to opportunities to practice these skills. Why therefore, is there still a gap between what industry wants and what HEIs provide and whose fault is it? Industry may be demanding more than an academic can deliver, in an already overcrowded curriculum with dwindling funding, particularly in an Irish context [2-3]. To close the gap, academics may need to expose students to professional skills in every module. This paper proposes a research study to explore how academics conceptualise their role in developing professional skills in engineering students.

Conference Key Areas: Skills and Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research, Curriculum Development

Keywords: Professional Skills, Phenomenography, Academic Conceptions of Teaching, Approaches to Teaching Inventory

INTRODUCTION

The author's interest in preparing engineering students for a successful career in industry stems from personal experience of recruiting, mentoring and managing graduates in civil and structural engineering consultancies. The range of skills, abilities and values of each graduate was varied, and it became apparent that academic achievement, whilst important, was not the defining skill for achieving early responsibility or promotion within the company. More often, the graduate who could communicate well and self-direct his/her work was given more responsibility and opportunity.

The intent in this paper is to present a plan for a PhD research study with two aims. The first is to summarise the research plan and proposed methodology. The second is to elicit critique and advice in the design of the study, including the research questions and the methods proposed.

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Influence of Accreditation Bodies and Industry

Accreditation requirements for engineering programmes serve as a framework for programme design. Several accrediting bodies including Engineers Ireland (EI), and the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) require degree programmes to include outcomes, which incorporate what may be considered professional skills [4-5]. These skills include; self-directed working, teamwork, multidisciplinary working, ethics, communication with the engineering community and with society at large. The EI programme outcomes have been developed in consultation with employers and should therefore address concerns about professional skills from an employer's perspective. Employers in Ireland however, still report that they are not satisfied with the level of competence of engineering graduates in non-technical skills. [1]. This suggests therefore, that although there are processes in place which should ensure that students have opportunities to develop these skills, there is a disparity between what the accreditation paperwork requires and the skills that students actually develop. One area where this disjoint may occur is in the classroom, and could be influenced by how the academic teaches or how the students learn.

1.2 Academic Conceptions of Teaching

Several studies report that although there is an awareness of the importance of developing non-technical skills within students, academics do not always feel adequately prepared to teach these skills, nor feel compelled to change their teaching pedagogy [6-10]. If we assume that academics are a key driver for change in engineering education, then we need to ascertain what constitutes good teaching or more importantly good learning in relation to developing professional skills. The theory of academic conceptions of teaching provides a lens through which to consider this aspect. When academics enter the classroom, they do so with prior conceptions of what constitutes good learning and teaching in their discipline. Prosser and Trigwell [11] purport that the academic's conception of teaching has a direct influence on how the students learn. Since this theory emerged in 1991, several researchers have produced varying categories of descriptions of the conceptions of teaching [11-14]. Prosser and Trigwell went a step further and created an Approaches to Teaching Inventory (ATI) survey instrument [11]. This can be used to identify which category best describes each survey respondent in a particular teaching context.

At the lowest level, the emphasis is on transmission of information and teacher focussed strategies with the result that students respond by accumulating information

and rote learning. The highest category signifies a conceptual change and student focussed approach where teachers focus on their students' own views or conceptions of the subject, rather than their own [11]. In this category, teaching pedagogies would likely include open discussions and debates so that students take ownership of their own views. One could conclude that the ability to critically examine an issue and defend a position requires practice in several of the professional skills that employers are seeking. One aspect of this research study intends to explore if the academic conceptions of teaching bear any relation to how academics feel about teaching **professional skills** in particular.

2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions centre around the experience of the academic in the classroom, although we are also interested in factors which may have influenced how the academic contemplates the relative importance of professional skills. This includes how the academic approaches teaching in general (with reference to the ATI) and previous training in different pedagogical approaches. The authors' background has influenced their own views on professional skills and so we want to investigate if academics with an industrial background have different views to those who have a purely academic background. This research study has three interlocking aspects as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Interlocking aspects of research study

The overarching research question is;

- What are the qualitatively different ways that academics experience and conceptualise teaching in engineering programmes in Ireland?

Sub-questions focusing on professional skills include;

- What are the qualitatively different ways that academics perceive what is meant by professional skills in engineering? How is the term 'professional skills' understood by engineering academics? What is the variation in academic's conceptions of what 'professional skills' mean?
- How do academics manifest their conceptions of teaching through their actions in teaching professional skills?
- What is the relationship (if any) between conceptions of teaching and academics' background in academia, industry or both?
- What is the relationship (if any) between conceptions of teaching and experiences of teaching professional skills?
- What is the correlation (if any) between conceptions of teaching professional skills and academic's backgrounds in academia, industry or both?

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Brief description of Phenomenography

The aim of the study is to build an understanding of academics' conceptions, perceptions and experiences of teaching professional skills. It is not to prove a hypothesis, to look at a particular case study nor a particular group of people. A descriptive method of enquiry was needed. Three research approaches were considered appropriate for the study; phenomenology, phenomenography and grounded theory. We determined that phenomenography would best answer the research questions.

Phenomenographers seek qualitatively different, but logically and hierarchically interconnected descriptions that a group of people experience in relation to a particular context [15]. Ference Marton, the original proposer of the term phenomenography, relates action and experience [16]. It follows that if we want to understand how people **handle** certain situations then we need to investigate how they **experience** those situations. "A capability for **acting** in a certain way reflects a capability **experiencing** something in a certain way. The latter does not cause the former, but they are logically intertwined" [16, p.111].

Phenomenography is proposed as an ideal fit for this research study for two reasons. Firstly, we believe that there are varied ways in which academics perceive, conceptualise and experience teaching professional skills. It is the variation we are interested in, not the commonalities which would be typical of a phenomenological study. The second reason is that a phenomenographic study is usually context bound. It refers to a particular instance that the interviewee is asked to reflect upon. We intend to investigate their experiences in relation to a particular context and not as an idea of teaching professional skills in the abstract.

3.2 Rationale and use of phenomenography in this research

This study aims to effect change in the way students are prepared for industry, particularly in relation to professional skills. This aligns well with the origins of phenomenography which was based in an educational setting. The study, while arguably based in education, focuses not on students but on the experiences and conceptions of academics.

There is merit in this approach as it is argued that previous research studies in science education have sought to develop prescriptive solutions to problems in teaching and learning and that this is not effective, that descriptive results are much more powerful [17]. Phenomenography allows us to look at how academics approach their teaching in a natural setting and how these approaches affect the outcome for students. Research output in a descriptive form will allow academics to reflect critically on their own practice, which can account for their own individual perceptions [17].

Despite initial assertions to the contrary [16,18], phenomenography can be considered a research approach, and the researcher uses whatever research methods most appropriate to the study. In this instance, we will undertake a two-phase approach. Phase One will comprise an online survey, the primary purpose of which is to collect background information on the participants forming the population sample. The survey responses will set the context for the research and will inform the interview questions for the main phenomenographic study, which is undertaken in Phase Two. Fig. 2. outlines the conceptual framework proposed for the research study.

Fig. 2. Conceptual framework of research study showing key milestones

3.3 Data Collection – Phase 1 Online Survey

The primary purpose of the Phase 1 online survey is to enable us to undertake purposive sampling for the Phase 2 (interview phase) of the study. However, it will also be used to assess engineering academics' attitudes towards learning and teaching in general using the Approaches to Teaching Inventory (ATI) [11]. This will allow us to compare and contrast against existing data banks for other disciplines.

3.4 Survey questions

The survey aims to collect information in the following categories:

- Gender
- Professional qualifications (both academic and professional organisations)
- Background career (engineer or other)
- Extent of industrial experience (what level; recruitment or mentoring of graduates)
- Extent of academic experience (what level; responsible for programme design)
- Previous experience of an accreditation event
- Ranking of the skills required to make a **good** engineering graduate.

As the survey will include both closed and open questions, quantitative and qualitative analysis will be possible. In particular, the following aspects may be analysed;

1. What percentage of academics have industry experience and furthermore were responsible for recruiting and/or mentoring graduates in industry?
2. What percentage of academics who teach engineers are engineers?
3. What percentage of academics believe that they only teach technical skills?
4. How does the ATI for engineering academics differ to other disciplines and is there a statistical significance between academics who have an engineering degree compared to others, or academics who have worked in industry compared to those who have not?
5. Is there a statistical difference between ATI for male and female academics?

6. What are the top 10 ranked professional skills for engineering graduates of today?
7. What percentage of academics have undertaken a teaching qualification? Is there a relationship between obtaining a teaching qualification and responses to the ATI?

3.5 Survey Method and Sample

The survey will be distributed electronically to all academics teaching on engineering programmes in all HEIs in Ireland. Only the author's own School will be excluded to avoid ethical issues [19]. A pilot survey will be trialled with respondents selected as meeting the requirements of the sample, but who will not be included in the final survey. They will be asked to give feedback on all aspects of the questionnaire including content, language, length and any ambiguity in the questions. In particular, the terms used in the question on ranking of professional skills will be reviewed in detail and these may have to be rephrased in order to extract the type of answers we intended.

3.6 Research Participants

It is important that the interviewees selected for the data collection are appropriate to the purpose of the research, by representing a large cross section of views about the research topic. A purposeful sample (research participants relevant to the central question) and maximisation of sample variation (broad range of views) is preferred [20]. It is important to select interviewees who offer what is described as "the best opportunity of manifesting the full extent of the various ways of experiencing the phenomenon" [21, p.6]. One opinion is that the researcher must not be swayed by being inclusive of gender or other cultural groups, which are in a phenomenographic sense, artificial distinctions. However, other researchers argue the opposite; that emotional responses are important and differ between the genders and "it would be useful for the phenomenographer in considering a purposive sample to include gender as a basis for ensuring adequate variation, to attend to sex differences in the analysis, and to choose to explore areas of learning central to women's as well as men's experiences" [22, p.224]. The sample for Phase 2 interviews will be selected bearing in mind the different facets of the research questions asked.

3.7 Data Collection – Phase 2 Interview Methodology

Whilst some texts suggest 25-30 interviews are required [20], others suggest that saturation can be achieved with 10-20 interviews [23]. It is initially intended to undertake 20 second stage interviews in addition to pilot interviews with two people who will not be included in the sample. The interviews will be undertaken by one researcher "in order to promote consistency in questioning and in the ways in which the responses are prompted and contrasted" [20, p.58].

3.8 Analytical Methods

Phenomenography aligns with a subjective ontology, where the researcher interprets the outcome of interviews with people. It is accepted that the people will construe the world in different ways, as opposed to there being one truth. In fact, in phenomenography, researchers do not make any assumptions about reality, nor do they intend that their research outputs represent the **truth**. The findings of a phenomenographic study are presented in outcome spaces; hierarchically ordered sets of categories of descriptions, identified by qualitatively different variations of experience of the phenomenon. Researchers aim to present outcome spaces that reflect the phenomenon, but researchers can only provide more or less complete outcomes, not right or wrong outcomes [23].

Through uncovering variation, we hope to identify different **categories of description** which show **themes of expanding awareness** of how teaching professional skills is conceptualised by academics. The hope is that the outcome spaces can show academics that there are **more complete ways** of conceptualising how we can teach professional skills and that this will encourage greater adoption by academics, even within technical subject areas.

4 SUMMARY

In this paper, we have provided a brief overview of a proposed PhD research study to elicit feedback from educational researchers in the field. We hope that the research we are about to conduct will contribute to placing increasing importance on teaching of professional skills. We hope that the outcomes will provide a framework for academic staff to reflect upon their own approach towards teaching professional skills in an engineering curriculum.

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